

Nature of Space And Dimension of Observable Universe and Beyond

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Abstract

My innovative research of space, space definition, types of space, space transformation methods result in space transformation law and space-matter transformation law. These space transformation methods and laws govern the nature of entire space. Finally I have covered the entire existence of space-time [1] and beyond by Dimension of Observable Universe and beyond. As we know the universe is defined as all space-time and their contents [2]. But questions are still open for higher dimension [3], singularity [4], gravity collapse at horizon of black hole [26], unified gravity [8], theory of everything [5], dark matter [6] [7], dark energy [6] [7], existence beyond the observable universe and for the space itself. These open questions have driven this scientific research of “Nature of Space and Dimension of Observable Universe and beyond”. My research findings indicate that the space itself is the entity with having physical properties. The space transforms/converts to matter and v/s. The higher dimension [2] is extended beyond the singularity [4], beyond the horizon of black hole and beyond the observable universe [2]. Although several researches have been done which include Minkowski space [8], General relativity [9] [10], Loop Quantum Gravity [3], String theory [11] [3] [12] [5], Higgs field [13], Aether medium [14], the questions are still open for higher dimension [2], unified gravity[8], dark matter [6] [7], dark energy [15] [16], theory of everything [5] and space beyond the universe. By researching the existence of matter, I found the existence of space was just accepted as the void, empty, and space-time background framework. There are well research attempts made to look into space-time as the entity and look for higher dimensions [2] by Loop Quantum Gravity [17] and String theory [12]. It became very important to define space and to research relationship between matter and space. And it would be not possible without defining higher dimensions [2]. My research reflects Dimension of Observable Universe and beyond accommodate all existence of observable universe and beyond the observable universe. The definition of space, type of space, space transformation and space-matter transformation perfectly describes existence of entire space & universe and its nature at very fundamental level. Also, the definitions of GODEYE, GODEYE Model explain the phenomena of universe expansion-contraction and phenomena of gravity at very fundamental level for the dimension of observable universe and beyond. It is the most accurate foundation to answer those open questions. It is the novelty in astrophysics and foundation of entire existence.

Keywords: *Higher Dimension; Space; Space transformation; GODEYE, Universe expansion-contraction; Gravity*

1 Introduction

Infinite Space thought travel during my Teenage. It was time starting from my 10th standard (Year 1994) for my interest in science, but I found personal note written during my first year of the college in year 1997.

During my 10th standard I read my science book the last lesson was about space shuttle, planets, sun, stars, light year, galaxy, supernova and so on... as per my best knowledge I travelled in that space shuttle during my 1st year of college. The travel was started at night time from the terrace of my house. I started my journey alone in the space shuttle towards the sky. There were only three space, me and space shuttle. Travel continued in straight line in the space to infinite. I thought that how far is the end of space that I could travel to reach to space end. I thought, to bring end of the space there must be boundary of matter where space ends. So, I travelled to infinite in the space where I reached matter boundary and space ends. Then I continued in same straight line through matter. The same question raised in my mind that how far is the end of the matter that I could travel to reach end of matter. Again I thought, to bring end of the matter there must be boundary of space. So, I travelled to infinite in the matter where I reached boundary of space and matter ends. Then I continued my journey through infinite space... again through infinite matter... and continues... It was brave journey of that teenager and he is still somewhere there in space with his infinite journey.

Just you try to look about the end rather in form of space or matter. To do this find yourself in it and try to imagine the picture in your mind. End of the universe is beyond one's imagination. Where is the god in the universe? Thou cannot able to find Thou self is out of the Universe or Thou is also contained in it? Because there is no end everywhere is the space and matter. How also god is contained in it? If so then who is capable to create the Universe? (Note: As a teenager I did not have understanding of the Universe [2] definition like modern science has and now I have).

Story ends here. But the questions during my teenage infinite journey are answered now. I recognize this as my teenage infinite-finite concept law from teenage ambitious thought dream.

After long break, I continued my research during the year 2018-2019, I got more questions about existence of space, existence of matter, entire existence, what is the space itself?, what is the matter itself? Where do all come from and how do all created? And what is the gravity?

In most existing scientific research the existence of space is just discussed and/or accepted as the vacuum, as the empty, as the void, as the space-time fabric [10], as the isotropic [18], as the homogenous [18], as the Minkowski space [8], with space geometry to define shape of the space [18], as the filled by any medium [14], and filled with major existence of dark matter [6] and dark energy [15]. In Standard Model [11], elementary particles are divided into two groups, elementary fermions and elementary bosons. Here, elementary fermions are the matter particles and the elementary bosons are the force particles. So, the fundamental matter existence is accepted as the quarks and leptons.

Below are some overview of existing research which match to my research subject up to certain extent.

Minkowski space: It is a combination of three-dimensional Euclidean space and time into a four-dimensional manifold. The mathematical model of space-time is called Minkowski space and it is essential in the description of general relativity [8].

General relativity: It mentions about gravitation effect between masses results from their wrapping of space-time. Here space-time tells matter how to move and matter tells space-time how to curve. The space-time is the back ground, curvature of space-time is the gravity [9] [10].

Loop Quantum gravity (LQG): It mentions that space-time itself made of discrete quanta, and quanta made of finite loops with nodes connecting them. It's has minimum value of length, area, volume and time. Space-time quanta volume resides at nodes intersection, loops represents two dimension area, large network of these loops and nodes called spin network. Space is defined by geometry of this spin network. And time is defined by movement of spin network. It is the theory of quantum gravity [3].

String theory: String theory is inspired by the standard model. The fundamental particles of the standard model replaced by even more fundamental one dimensional strings. String theory describes how the string propagate from the space and interact with each other. These strings vibrate in many extra space-time dimensions. It claims to be Theory of Everything [11] [3] [12] [5].

The theory of aether: It was postulated by physicists that aether permeated all throughout space, providing a medium through which light could travel in a vacuum. But later through experiments by physicists, it was declared that aether does not exist [14].

Higgs field: It exist everywhere in the space and having its elementary particle called Higgs boson. Any elementary particle while passing through this Higgs field will interact with Higgs boson and obtain the mass [19].

Dark matter: It is postulated by physicists that dark matter contributes 27% of the total mass-energy content in observable universe [6] [7].

Dark energy: It is postulated by physicists that dark energy contributes 68% of the total mass-energy in observable universe [15] [16].

Ordinary matter: In standard model it is accepted as the fundamental matter particles called fundamental fermions. They are ‘quarks and antiquarks’ and ‘leptons and antileptons’ [11].

These existing researches address different individual subject. Some of them have partial matching scientific concept to my research subject. But even by putting all together and/or individual do not give satisfied complete answer to my research questions.

General relativity: It collapse at singularity inside the black hole and big bang. It does not fit with quantum mechanics. Due to this General relativity is incomplete. General relativity treats space-time as a bending of the continuous back ground of space-time not as the discrete particle that confer a force [10] [9]. It does not talk about what is the space-time itself? How and from where the existence of space-time and matter come from?

Loop Quantum gravity (LQG): It extends general relativity concept with different structure of space-time. It really talks about space-time made of discrete quanta. But Loop Quantum gravity (LQG) is theory of quantum gravity only [9].

String theory: It talks about standard model by replacing fundamental particles of standard model by even more fundamental one dimensional strings. Here, Space-time is the background in which strings vibrate but it does not talk about what is the space itself? Yes, string theory talks about extra-dimensional space-time in which strings vibrate [3] [20] [21].

The theory of aether: It did not mention about space itself? , not mentioned about space-time and not mentioned the properties of aether itself. The experiments by physicists did not show any presence of aether [14].

Higgs field: It talks about Higgs field everywhere in the space. And how particles obtain the mass [19]. It does not talk about the Higgs field existence come from? It does not talk about the existence of space-time and matter come from?

Dark matter: Dark matter is unknown form of matter and it is limited to mass-energy content of observable universe [6] [7]. The scientist are still in search of dark matter.

Dark energy: Dark energy is unknown form of energy and it is limited to mass-energy content of observable universe. It is responsible for expansion of the universe [15] [16]. The scientist are still in search of dark energy.

Ordinary matter: Ordinary matter existence is accepted in form of elementary fermions. In the past decades several research have redefined elementary matter particles [11]. And questions are still open that what is the ultimate matter particle? Matter particle existence come from where?

None of the above theory as the individual and all together describes entire existence and true nature of entire existence. Instead it describes partial nature of entire existence which may not 100% correct to accept. Especially, I feel impressed with Loop Quantum gravity (LQG) as it describes space-time as the quanta and quanta mechanics [3]. Also, I feel impressed with one dimensional string and extra dimensions [3]. Moreover, Concept of Aether medium which occupy the empty space [14], Higgs field which is everywhere in the universe [13], Dark matter contributes 27% of the observable universe [6], Dark energy contributes 68% of the observable universe [15], Ordinary matter contributes 5% of the observable universe [6]. All these Aether medium, Higgs field, dark matter, and dark energy concerning about space & mass-energy or unknown existence part of the space & universe while ordinary matter is the known part of the observable universe [2]. But the gap still remains to answer what is the space itself? What is the matter itself? Where do all come from and how do all created? The gap still remains to unite classical mechanics [22] and quantum mechanics [23], gap still remains for entire existence and true nature of the observable universe and beyond.

These questions must be answered to know true nature of entire existence and foundation of entire existence. So, I continue research and after long break of two decades, during year 2018-2022. The right question gives the

right answer. In this process firstly I research space and matter, and defined pure space by the year 2019. Which resulted with more research of space transformation, space-matter transformation by the year 2021. While gravity was already question for me that what is it? And how does it work? Even after research done during year 2002-2005. And with more theoretical research done about space, matter, energy, mass, time, gravity during year 2018-2022. Final result, the pure space definition, types of space, space transformation, and space-matter transformation together answer about space, space-time, and fundamental nature of entire existence and beyond. It became challenging for me to establish through end to end connectivity for the entire existence of space, space-time and beyond, to establish universal and beyond scientific nature, to establish universal and beyond scientific relationship (Which includes singularity [4], gravity at singularity [4] and beyond), and to unite classical world and quantum world into one. By the early year 2022, this universal and beyond nature of existence have been solved, and unification of classical mechanics [22] and quantum mechanics [23], singularity [4] and space-time have been considered with research done about 'Dimension of Observable Universe and beyond'. And this article starts from there on.

My research defines the space itself as the entity, describes true nature of space and matter, describes existence of matter, and true nature of entire existence. This entire existence and its working is covered by 'Dimension of Observable Universe and beyond'. These new simplified dimensions and methods unites classical mechanics [22] and quantum mechanics [23] into one, also unite the beyond.

My findings explain true nature of entire universe and beyond. This is novelty in theoretical astrophysics research, with new methods, new definitions and new laws. The existing scientific information do not truly mention about definition of the space and nature of the space, existence of matter, space and matter relationship, dimension of the entire space, dimension of the universe, and existence of the universe, and from where and how the entire existence emerge at fundamental level?

With the new definition of space, it simplifies the various concept of space like vacuum, void, empty, and filled with medium by uniting them all to one fundamental space.

With the new definition of space, methods and laws, it simplifies the various theory for type of space, and shape of space like isotropic [2], homogeneous [2], and various geometry concepts for shapes of the space by uniting all to one unique space standard.

With new space and space-time structure, it simplifies the various types of space-time fabric [10] like general relativity's continuous space-time fabric [10], Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) quanta space-time fabric [3], extra dimensional space in string theory [3] and unite all to one unique space-time standard.

With new 'End to End dimension', it simplifies the various dimensions like extra dimension [2], higher dimension [2] by uniting all to one standard dimension.

In fact it more correct answers for those previous research done and more answers about any medium, Higgs field [13], elementary matter [11], dark matter [6], and dark energy [15]. It adds more value to standard model [11] for existence of fundamental matter particle with true nature.

It explains space existence and matter existence, and establishes true nature in between space-time [1] and fundamental matter particles. The defined end to end dimension here, which ultimately connect matter world to the space world and v/s. It establishes truly scientific relationship in between space world and matter world.

The definition of GODEYE and developed GODEYE Model explain the phenomena of universe expansion-contraction, and define gravity and define gravitation force at very fundamental level for the dimension of observable universe and beyond.

2 Dimension $P(X, Y, Z, T)$ and $Q(X, Y, Z, T)$, and Totality of Existence

Four Dimensions are commonly known to us. They are three spatial dimensions to determine position, location, shape, size and volume of the object. The fourth dimension is a dimension of time, dimension is one way to measure physical change. Three spatial dimensions denoted by (X, Y, Z) [24] and Time dimension is denoted by (T) . So, they together, four dimensions denoted by (X, Y, Z, T) [25].

In our daily life experience, we observe many objects around us with different shapes, sizes, volumes, locations, positions, changes and colors. We identify these objects by our eye vision and/or by physical touch and/or by feeling with processing by our mind and/or imagination by our mind. In the world of science and in general these objects are known as the 3D objects. Here, 3D represents three dimensions of the object. These three dimensions (3D) are used to know the sizes, volumes, locations and positions of the objects. For example the size of the room that we are living in, it has height, length and width. We often label them as the X, Y, Z of the room. And these 3D (X, Y, Z) values, we multiply to calculate size or space of the room.

Many of the 3D objects like bacteria, human, animal, computer, car, train and aero plane have comparatively more complex shapes. For these objects we have to apply 3D geometry function to calculate sizes, volumes, positions and locations of the objects.

The 3D objects are either stationary or moving or changing, for those objects which are moving and changing positions and locations, some objects keep changing its sizes, volumes, energy, temperature and other properties too. For such additional physical changes and chemical changes or physical events or chemical events, we have additional Fourth dimension of time (T) .

So, Dimension of any object can be described by its four dimension 4D (X, Y, Z, T) [25]. Likewise the physical Universe is described by space-time. So, I take space-time as the 4D dimension of the Universe [2].

Following from above discussion about space-time 4D (X, Y, Z, T) , now I derive two 4D planes called $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ and $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$. Fig-1 below demonstrate dimensions $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ and $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$, its properties, scope and entire existence within.

Fig-1. End to End Dimensions $P(X, Y, Z, T)$ and $Q(X, Y, Z, T)$ and Entire Existence

$P(x, y, z, t)$ is the 4D plane of ‘space-time (pure space-time only)’ and $Q(x, y, z, t)$ is also the 4D plane of the ‘space-time (space-time with matter)’. So, there are the space-time and matter only in between the range of $P(x, y, z, t)$ 4D plane and $Q(x, y, z, t)$ 4D plane. But both planes have different properties of space and different properties of time. So, both planes are totally distinct in existence.

2.1 Dimension $P(X, Y, Z, T)$

$P(x, y, z, t)$ is the dimension of pure space. Pure space is constant in nature so the dimension is also known as the $C(x, y, z, t)$. It is the dimension where space becomes pure, all of Newtonian mass [26], Gravitational mass [26], Inertial mass [26], Atomic mass [26], Elementary mass [26] [11] become zero, all of four fundamental forces [27] becomes zero, and pressure [28] becomes zero, absence of matter (particle less), absence of fundamental temperature [28] and exist infinite pure energy and exist pure time only. $P(x, y, z, t)$ describes and having existence of the pure space and pure time with pure energy only. Pure space is just only one in count with dimension $P(x, y, z, t)$. Pure space is the uniform and eternal with dimension $P(x, y, z, t)$. And $P(x, y, z, t)$ is the infinite dimension.

2.2 Dimension $Q(X, Y, Z, T)$

$Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$, represents dimension of the space-time with matter. The ‘space-time with matter’ is variable in nature so the dimension is also known as the $V_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$. Here, the $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ is the finite dimension of space-time which transformed/converted from C space, with having matter (particle), with having all Newtonian mass [26], Gravitational mass, Inertial mass, Atomic mass, Elementary mass, with having all four fundamental forces [27], with having pressure, having fundamental temperature and having variable energy with variable dimensions.

Space-time of the $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ comprise of quantum particles, elementary matter particles, various forms of mass-energy, atoms, molecules, planets, moons, stars, star systems, galaxies [2] and having variable dimensions.

$Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ are the multiple dimensions in count and each $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ dimension is separate than other $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ dimension. It is the transient dimension.

2.3 $P(X, Y, Z, T)$ and $Q(X, Y, Z, T)$

Both $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ and $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ are the dimensions of space-time but both have different properties of space and different properties of time. They represent two different 4D planes, these two planes are opposite to each other with opposite dimensional properties to each other.

In above Fig-1, from $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$. It shows P space transforms to I space, I space transforms to V space, V space transforms to C space and C space transforms to space-time with matter (Refer: Transformation of the space, Space and Matter transformation).

In above Fig-1, from $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$. It shows space-time with matter transforms to C space, C space transform to V space, V space transform to I space, I space transform to P space (Refer: Transformation of the space, Space and Matter transformation).

Here the Space-time with matter is the transient of charged space-time and ultimately transient of pure space-time. So, the space-time with matter is created from and emerged out from pure space-time. The $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ is created from and emerged out from $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$. So, the $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ is the transient dimension of $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$.

2.4 *Totality of Existence*

As described in above Fig-1, there are two end to end 4D space-time planes and they are $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$. From $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$, in sequence they contained P space plane, I space plane, V space plane, C space plane and plane of space-time with matter.

From $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$, in sequence they contained plane of space-time with matter, C space plane, V space plane, I space plane and P space plane.

In general this Dimension $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ represents existence of all quantum particles, elementary matter particles, various forms of mass-energy, atoms, molecules, the world we human live-in, planets, moons, stars, star systems, galaxies, physical universe [2]. As this $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ can be extended to ‘C space plane’ and ‘V space plane’.

Dimensional planes of P space, I space, V space, C space represent all the space existence.

So, Everything that exist and that non-exist fall within the range of these dimension $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ and dimension $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$.

3 **Space and Type of space, Definition of P space**

Space is simply defined “the matter less volume”. The space itself is the entity and having specific physical properties.

3.1 *Type of space*

There are four types of space, and they are P space, I space, V space, C space. Which are described in above Fig-1, and they all fall within range of $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ and $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$.

P space in full form is called as Pure space. And P space is composed of unit P space elements and the unit element is called as PS_{UE} .

I space in full form is called as Invisible space. And I space is composed of unit I space elements and the unit element is called as IS_{UE} .

V space in full form is called as Vibrating space. And V space is composed of unit V space elements and the unit element is called as VS_{UE} .

C space in full form is called Charged space. And C space is composed of unit C space elements and the unit element is called as CS_{UE} .

3.2 *Definition of P Space*

In this article, I keep space definition limited to P space only. And, P space is defined here with reference to Dimension $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ and with reference to Dimension $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$.

3.2.1 *P space definition with reference to Dimension $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$*

P space – “It is the pure space. It is the space with infinite volume, surfaceless, boundaryless, shapeless, positionless, dimensionless (absence of four fundamental dimensions), massless (absence of all fundamental mass (Newtonian mass, Gravitational mass, Inertial mass, Atomic mass, Elementary mass)), motionless (movementless, vibrationless, waveless), mass-energy contentless (due to absence of all fundamental mass (Newtonian mass, Gravitational mass, Inertial mass, Atomic mass, Elementary particle mass)), (forceless (absence of four fundamental forces), matterless (particleless), temperatureless (absence fundamental temperature), with pure time (absence fundamental time) and having infinite pure energy (absence of energy of I space plane, V space plane, C space plane and $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ plane)”.

Explanation: For simple understanding, Dimension $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ is the dimension of the world we live in and we define the pure space from there. While the pure space is the beyond the world we live in. At the pure space the dimension $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ does not exist. So, at pure space that all the fundamental mass-energy contents of the world we live in do not exist. Fundamental physical properties [28] like mass, energy, force, power, pressure, temperature of the world we live in do not exist in pure space. The temperature becomes irrelevant in pure space. The fundamental time (time dimension of the world we live in) transform to pure time dimension. And the fundamental energy (energy of the world we live in) transform to pure energy.

3.2.2 *P space definition with reference to Dimension $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$*

P space – “It is the pure space. It is the space with infinite volume, with pure dimension ($P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$, where $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}=0$), with pure mass (mass in pure dimension only), motionless (movementless, vibrationless, waveless), pure mass-energy content (mass-energy content in pure dimension only), with pure force (Force in pure dimension only), matterless (particleless), with pure temperature (Temperature in pure dimension only), with pure time (Time in pure dimension only) and having infinite pure energy (absence of energy of I space plane, V space plane, C space plane and $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ plane)”.

“OR”

P space – “It is the pure space. It is the space with infinite volume, surfaceless, boundaryless, shapeless, positionless, with pure dimension ($P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$, where $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}=0$), with pure mass (absence of all fundamental mass (Newtonian mass, Gravitational mass, Inertial mass, Atomic mass, Elementary mass)), motionless (movementless, vibrationless, waveless), pure mass-energy content (absence of all fundamental mass-energy content), with pure force (absence of four fundamental forces), matterless (particleless), with pure temperature (absence of fundamental temperature), with pure time ($P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$, where $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}=0$) and having infinite pure energy (absence of energy of I space plane, V space plane, C space plane and $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ plane)”.

Explanation: For simple understanding, Dimension $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ is the dimension of beyond the world we live in and we define the pure space from there. At the pure space the dimension $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ does not exist. So, at pure space that all the fundamental mass-energy contents of the world we live in do not exist. Fundamental physical properties [28] like mass, energy, force, power, pressure, temperature of the world we live in do not exist in pure space. The temperature becomes irrelevant in pure space. But pure space exist with pure energy, pure mass, pure force, pure temperature and pure time.

4 Transformation of the space

There are four types of space, and they are P space, I space, V space, C space. Here, I space, V space, C space are transformed forms of P space. below Fig-2, describes basic model of P space element (PS_{UE}), I space element (IS_{UE}), V space element (VS_{UE}), C space element (CS_{UE}) transformation.

Fig-2. Space Element transformation

In above Fig-2, it demonstrate, from top to bottom:

- P space element/elements (PS_{UE}) transform/convert to I space element/elements (IS_{UE}),
- I space element/elements (IS_{UE}) transform/convert to V space element/elements (VS_{UE}),
- V space element/elements (VS_{UE}) transform/convert to C space element/elements (CS_{UE}).

In above Fig-2, it demonstrate, from bottom to top:

- C space element/elements (CS_{UE}) transform/convert to V space element/elements (VS_{UE}),
- V space element/elements (VS_{UE}) transform/convert to I space element/elements (IS_{UE}),
- I space element/elements (IS_{UE}) transform/convert to P space element/elements (PS_{UE}).

As the space element(s) transformation demonstrated here in Fig-2, the result is described in Fig-1, from $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$. It shows P space transforms to I space, I space transforms to V space, V space transforms to C space. And the result is ‘Space transformation law (First Law)’ as described in Fig-4 and Fig-5.

As the space element(s) transformation demonstrated here in Fig-2, the result is described in Fig-1, from $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$. It shows C space transform to V space, V space transform to I space, I space transform to P space. And the result is ‘Space transformation law (First Law)’ as described in Fig-4 and Fig-5.

5 Space and Matter transformation

There are four types of space, and they are P space, I space, V space, C space. Here, I space, V space, C space are transformed forms of P space. below Fig-3, describes basic model of P space element (PS_{UE}), I space element (IS_{UE}), V space element (VS_{UE}), C space element (CS_{UE}), matter element transformation.

In below Fig-3, it demonstrate, from top to bottom:

- P space element/elements (PS_{UE}) transform/convert to I space element/elements (IS_{UE}),
- I space element/elements (IS_{UE}) transform/convert to V space element/elements (VS_{UE}),
- V space element/elements (VS_{UE}) transform/convert to C space element/elements (CS_{UE})
- C space element/elements (CS_{UE}) transform/convert to matter element/elements (fundamental matter particle).

In below Fig-3, it demonstrate, from bottom to top:

- Matter element/elements (fundamental matter particle) transform/convert to C space element/elements (CS_{UE}),
- C space element/elements (CS_{UE}) transform/convert to V space element/elements (VS_{UE}),
- V space element/elements (VS_{UE}) transform/convert to I space element/elements (IS_{UE}),

- I space element/elements (IS_{UE}) transform/convert to P space element/elements (PS_{UE}).

Fig-3. Space element to Matter element transformation and v/s

As the space element(s)-matter element(s) transformation demonstrated here in Fig-3, the result described in Fig-1, from $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$. It shows P space transforms to I space, I space transforms to V space, V space transforms to C space and C space transforms to space-time with matter. And the result is 'Space-Matter Transformation Law (Second Law)'.

As the space element(s)-matter element(s) transformation demonstrated here in Fig-3, the result described in Fig-1, from $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$. It shows space-time with matter transforms to C space, C space transform to V space, V space transform to I space, I space transform to P space. And the result is 'Space-Matter Transformation Law (Second Law)'.

6 Space transformation law (First Law)

Fig-4. Space transformation law

Above Fig-4 demonstrates nature of the First Law. In above, A represents $PS_{UE(s)}$, A' represents $CS_{UE(s)}$, B represents Pure space, B' represents Charged space.

First Law is derived from space transformation method as demonstrated and described in above 'Transformation of the space' and it is mentioned as under in different ways. First Law:

“When PS_{UE} transform to CS_{UE} Then space transform from shapeless space to spherical shape space”

Or

“When PS_{UE} transform to CS_{UE} Then space bends to spherical”

Or

“When PS_{UE} transform to CS_{UE} Then space transform from shapeless space to curve shape space”

Or

“When PS_{UE} transform to CS_{UE} Then space bends to curve”

Or

“When PS_{UE} transform to CS_{UE} Then space transform from shapeless P space to spherical C space”

Or

“When PS_{UE} transform to CS_{UE} Then space transform from shapeless P space to curve C space”

It describes more clearly about ‘space transformation law’. When space element(s) transform from A to A’, then space transform from B to B’. (Where, A is $PS_{UE}(s)$, A’ is $CS_{UE}(s)$, B is Pure space, B’ is Charged space).

The above Fig-4, can represent alternate way as describes in below Fig-5, with same meaning about ‘space transformation law’.

Fig-5. Alternate way, Space transformation law

It also describes when Space element(s) transform from A to A', then space transform from B to B'.

(Where, A is PS_{UE}(s), A' is CS_{UE}(s), B is Pure space, B' is Charged space).

So, with above simple explanation, the first law demonstrates “when A transform to A' then B transform to B'”. In this law two events A to A' and B to B' are happening jointly, and both events depend on each other.

7 Space-Matter Transformation Law (Second Law)

Second Law is derived from space-matter transformation method as demonstrated and described in above ‘Space and Matter transformation’.

Second Law “Space converts/transforms to Matter and Matter converts/transforms to Space”

It is the law which explains the existence of all the matter in the universe [2]. Each and every matter object in the universe like quantum particles, elementary matter particles, subatomic, atoms, molecules, moons, planets, stars are the transformed form of the space.

In our daily life what we can see with our open eyes, like food, water, house, paper, pen, book, computer, mobile, human, animal, bicycle, car, train, road, aero plane, land, rock, mountain, water, ocean, fire, iron, gold, earth, moon, planets, sun, stars all these made of/made from space. All these are transformed form of the space.

8 GODEYE and GODEYE MODEL

8.1 GODEYE

Definition of GODEYE “At the same moment of the time which has vision perpendicular outward and has vision perpendicular inward on unit surface of each and every unit element that is called GODEYE”

Each and every object(s), each and every element(s) which exist between Dimension P_(X, Y, Z, T) and Dimension Q_(X, Y, Z, T) are under continuous GODEYE vision for all the time.

8.2 GODEYE Model

In this section we learn about GODEYE working by applying to any object. When we apply GODEYE to any object, we can say the object itself has perpendicular outward and perpendicular inward vision and the each unit

element of the main object has perpendicular outward and perpendicular inward vision at the same moment of the time.

Here perpendicular outward vision and perpendicular inward vision, we can say the “Vision” is the “Act”. Now we apply GODEYE definition in general form with Act. Then it is called GODEYE Model Act. This Act can be Vision, can be Dimension, can be Force, can be Flow, can be Transformation, can be Effect and Act itself.

When Act is the Act, it is called GODEYE Model Act.

When Act is the Vision, it is called GODEYE Model Vision.

When Act is the Dimension, it is called GODEYE Model Dimension.

When Act is the Force, it is called GODEYE Model Force.

When Act is the Flow, it is called GODEYE Model Flow.

When Act is the Transformation, it is called GODEYE Model Transformation.

When Act is the Effect, it is called GODEYE Model Effect.

When we apply GODEYE Act to any object, it is called GODEYE Model Act on that particular object.

GODEYE Model Act defined as “the object itself has perpendicular outward and perpendicular inward vision and the each unit element of the main object has perpendicular outward and perpendicular inward vision at the same moment of the time”

So, when we apply GODEYE definition for any Act to any object it’s called GODEYE Model Act on that object. Or can say the object is under GODEYE Model Act.

Let us continue for Vision Act on the object and we can say the object has GODEYE Model Vision.

In Fig-6 below, we are applying GODEYE Model Vision to sphere object Z.

Fig-6. GODEYE

Working of the GODEYE Model Vision for sphere Z is described as under.

Let us apply GOD EYE Vision model to above sphere object Z.

Point A: is the point object on most outer spherical surface of sphere object Z.

Point B: is the point object on inner spherical circumference of sphere object Z.

Point C: is the central point object of sphere object Z

Most outer spherical circumference of sphere object Z

Point object A is on outer spherical circumference of sphere object Z. With applied GOD EYE Model Vision on point object A, it has perpendicular vision to outward and perpendicular vision inward to the center of the sphere object Z as represented in Fig-6 above. Like this each and every point object on most outer spherical circumference has perpendicular vision outward and perpendicular vision toward the center of the sphere.

All inner spherical circumferences of sphere object Z

In Fig-6 above we can see many more points toward the center of the sphere object Z. All those point objects lie on inner spherical circumferences. All those spherical circumferences represent inner sphere objects with the same center point. Point object B is on those inner spherical circumferences of sphere object Z. With applied GODEYE Model Vision on point object B, it has perpendicular vision to outward and perpendicular vision to the center of the sphere object Z as represented in Fig-6 above. Like this with applied GOD EYE Model Vision to all those point objects on inner spherical circumferences of those inner sphere objects have perpendicular vision outward and perpendicular vision to the center of the sphere object Z.

Center of sphere object Z

In above Fig-6 the point object C is the center point object of sphere object Z. With applied GODEYE Model Vision it has perpendicular vision outward and perpendicular vision inward. For more details, The GOD EYE Model Vision applied to Point object C as represented and described in Fig-7 below.

Like this with applied GODEYE Model Vision on sphere object Z, all the point objects on most outer spherical surface to all inner spherical surfaces have perpendicular vision inward and perpendicular outward at the same moment of the time.

By Integration of the above processes, we can say the sphere as the individual object has the spherical vision perpendicular outward from the surface and perpendicular inward from the spherical surface.

AND

By Integration of the above processes, we can say all the inner spherical circumferences including central spherical circumference's spherical bodies have spherical vision perpendicular outward from their surfaces and perpendicular inward from their surfaces.

Next, In Fig-7 below, we continue applying GODEYE Model Vision to point element objects on outer spherical circumference, on inner spherical circumference and center point element of object of sphere object Z.

Fig-7. GODEYE Model

Working of the GODEYE Model Vision for sphere Z and for point element objects on all spherical circumferences and for central point element object of the sphere Z are described as under.

Level 1: represents spherical object Z

Level 2: represents point object A on most outer spherical surface of sphere object Z

Level 2: represents point object C at the center of sphere object Z

Level 3: represents point object AA on most outer spherical surface of point object A

Level 3: represents point object AC at the center of point object A

Level 3: represents point object CA on most outer spherical surface of point object C

Level 3: represents point object CC at the center of point object C

Point object A, point object B, point object C, are point objects of sphere Z

Point object AA, point object AB, point object AC are point objects of point object A

Point object CA, point object CB, point object CC are point objects of point object C

Point object AAA, point object AAB, point object AAC are point objects of point object AA

Point object ACA, point object ACB, point object ACC are point objects of point object AC

Point object CAA, point object CAB, point object CAC are point objects of point object CA

Point object CCA, point object CCB, point object CCC are point objects of point object CC

Level 1: represents

Sphere object Z and it has vision following GODEYE Model Vision as described in Fig-6 above.

Point object A, point object B, point object C, are point objects of sphere Z

Level 2: represents

Point object A on most outer spherical surface of sphere Z and Point object A has vision following GODEYE

Model Vision as described in Fig-6 above (same as sphere Z)

Point object AA, point object AB, point object AC are point objects of point object A

Level 2: represents

Point object C at the center object of sphere Z and Point object C has vision following GODEYE Model Vision as described in Fig-6 above (same as sphere Z)

Point object CA, point object CB, point object CC are point objects of point object C

Level 3: represents

Point object AA on most outer spherical surface of point object A and Point object AA has vision following GODEYE Model Vision as described in Fig-6 above (same as sphere Z)

Point object AAA, point object AAB, point object AAC are point objects of point object AA

Level 3: represents

Point object AC at the center object of point object A and Point object AC has vision following GODEYE Model Vision as described in Fig-6 above (same as sphere Z)

Point object ACA, point object ACB, point object ACC are point objects of point object AC

Level 3: represents

Point object CA on most outer spherical surface of point object C and Point object CA has vision following GODEYE Model Vision as described in Fig-6 above (same as sphere Z)

Point object CAA, point object CAB, point object CAC are point objects of point object CA

Level 3: represents

Point object CC at the center object of point object C and Point object CC has vision following GODEYE

Model Vision as described in Fig-6 above (same as sphere Z)

Point object CCA, point object CCB, point object CCC are point objects of point object CC

Likewise all point object B, point object AB, point object CB, Point object AAA, point object AAB, point object AAC, Point object ACA, point object ACB, point object ACC, Point object CAA, point object CAB, point object CAC, Point object CCA, point object CCB, point object CCC have vision following GODEYE Model Vision as described in Fig-6 above (same as sphere Z).

Level n: represents n numbers of level

Point objects m are m numbers of point objects of n numbers of level. And all point objects m have GODEYE Model Vision as described in Fig-6 above (same as sphere Z).

Level 1, level 2, level 3... Level n are acting at the same moment of time. So, we find sphere Z and all the point elements of sphere Z have spherical vision perpendicular outward and spherical vision perpendicular inward at the same moment of time. There is nothing left without vision as the act is in the same moment of time.

9 Universe Expansion and Contraction

The phenomena of universe expansion and contraction is the change in universe volume itself. Which is happening due to space elements and matter elements transformation.

With reference to $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$

‘Matter elements’ transform to ‘C space elements (CS_{UE})’ transform to ‘V space elements (VS_{UE})’ transform to ‘I space elements (IS_{UE})’ transform to ‘P space elements (PS_{UE})’ is the phenomena of expansion of the universe.

And

‘P space elements (PS_{UE})’ transform to ‘I space elements (IS_{UE})’ transform to ‘V space elements (VS_{UE})’ transform to ‘C space elements (CS_{UE})’ transform to ‘Matter elements’ is the phenomena of contraction of the universe.

10 Gravity and Gravitational Force

Before we learn about Gravity and Gravitation Force, let us recall GODEYE Model to define GODEYE Model Flow, GODEYE Model Transformation, and GODEYE Model Force.

GODEYE Model and When Act is Flow, it is called GODEYE Model Flow

GODEYE Model Flow defined as “the object itself has perpendicular outward and perpendicular inward Flow, and the each unit element of the main object has perpendicular outward and perpendicular inward Flow at the same moment of the time”

GODEYE Model and When Act is Transformation, it is called GODEYE Model Transformation

GODEYE Model Transformation (X' formation) defined as “the object itself has perpendicular outward and perpendicular inward Transformation (X' formation), and the each unit element of the main object has perpendicular outward and perpendicular inward Transformation (X' formation) at the same moment of the time”

GODEYE Model and When Act itself is Force, it is called GODEYE Model Force

GODEYE Model Force defined as “the object itself has perpendicular outward and perpendicular inward Force, and the each unit element of the main object has perpendicular outward and perpendicular inward Force at the same moment of the time”

In Fig-8 below, we are applying above GODEYE Models to define Gravity and Gravitation Force.

Fig-8. Phenomena of Gravity

From above Fig-8 , we define Gravity and Gravitation Force, and describes scope of gravity and its force as under.

10.1 Gravity

Definition of Gravity: Transformation/Flowing of energy following ‘GODEYE MODEL Transformation/Flow’ from Dimension $P(X, Y, Z, T)$ to Dimension $Q(X, Y, Z, T)$ is called Gravity.

Definition of Anti-Gravity: Transformation/Flowing of energy following ‘GODEYE MODEL Transformation/Flow’ from Dimension $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to Dimension $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ is called Anti-Gravity.

10.2 Gravitation Force

Definition of Gravitational Force: Force applicable for transformation/flowing of energy following ‘GODEYE MODEL Transformation/Flow’ from Dimension $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to Dimension $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ is called Gravitational Force.

Definition of Anti-Gravitational Force: Force applicable for transformation/flowing of energy following ‘GODEYE MODEL Transformation/Flow’ from Dimension $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to Dimension $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ is Anti-Gravitational Force.

10.3 Scope of the Gravity

Gravity is the continuous effect one each and every element from Dimension $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to Dimension $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ and from Dimension $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to Dimension $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$

Gravity applies to all the objects including Space, CMB, COSMOS, Multi universe, Universe, Galaxy, Black hole, Star, planet, atomic, sub atomic, fundamental particles, Quantum particles which exist between Dimension $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ and Dimension $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$.

Gravity works on each and every object(s), each and every element(s) for all the time and everywhere.

11 Dimension of Observable Universe and beyond

Everything that exist within observable universe [2] and beyond all fall within range of $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ and $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$. Thus the dimension $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ and $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ together called as the ‘dimension of totality of existence’ or ‘dimension of observable universe and beyond’.

It is the dimension of space-time and beyond. It is the dimension of totality of existence universe and existence beyond. It is 'end to end dimension' everything that exist and that non-exist fall within this dimensions. We can also called as the 'finite-infinite dimension'.

12 Results and Discussion

With my continuous deep interest in science since my 10th standard (Year 1994). In the year 1997, I had wrote personal note about my "thought infinite journey to space". During year 2002-2005, again I wrote personal note about relativity which combined examples from academics and my daily journey experience by train to my working station and wrote about gravitation with many questions in mind, with daily observations, with daily life experiences.

Lastly my deep theoretical research from 2018-2022, which I present here in this research article. It says about existing space-time dimension (X, Y, Z, T) [25]. From this dimension I have derived to two dimensions, $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ and $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$, and associate these dimensions with the space-time only and space-time with matter. These dimensions $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ and $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ contain the entire existence of the space and entire existence of the universe [2] within. In basic this existence divided into two categories of space and matter. The definition of the space as the entity with physical properties, it further derives transformation of space in various forms of space and transformation of space element(s) to matter particle(s) and v/s. These transformation methods explain fundamental nature of space and matter within $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ and $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$. Finally these changes of space element(s) derives 'First Law of Space Transformation', and changes of space element(s) and changes of matter element(s) derives 'Second Law of Space-Matter Transformation'.

The most popular theories of general relativity [29] [10], Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) [17] [3], Higgs field [13], aether medium [14], string theory [12], theory of everything [5], dark matter [6], ordinary matter [11] and dark energy [15] have matching subject within my research. My research is partially in contrast with general relativity in terms of existence of the space and it is partially inline in terms of bending of the space [10]. My research is partially in line with Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) in terms of existence of the space quanta [17] [3]. My research is partially in contrast with string theory in terms of existence of the space and it is partially in line

with string theory in terms of extra dimensions [12] [20] [3]. My research is partially in contrast with Higgs field in terms of existence of the Higgs field in the space and it is partially in line with universal existence of Higgs field [13] [19]. My research is partially in contrast with Aether in terms of existence of the medium in the space and it is partially in line with concept of filling the space by aether medium [14]. The model presented here also consider unification of classical mechanics [22] and quantum mechanics [23] including singularity [4]. Actually it presents the true nature of space within the observable universe [2] and beyond.

My research may address most mysterious subjects in recent days. The space itself is the major part of existence within observable universe [2] and beyond. The major space of the universe [2] is in form of V space and C space. These forms of V space and C space have energy and mass which directly matching to the most discussed concept of dark energy [15] and dark matter [6] which constitute major part of the universe [2].

Also, my research may put more light on research field of elementary particle [11], duality nature of quantum particle [23], standard model [11] and theory of everything [5].

Here, the definitions of gravity and gravitation force overcome the limitations of gravitational theories of Sir Isaac Newton and Sir Albert Einstein at very fundamental level.

This is at very basic and limited research. In this research the space is composed of unit elements. Like pure space has unit element PS_{UE} , I space has unit element IS_{UE} , V space has unit element VS_{UE} , C space has unit element CS_{UE} . In the space transformation and space-matter transformation methods, it is not exactly mentioned that either it is single unit element or multiple unit elements are transforming. Here, the $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ is variable 4D plane of the 'space-time (space-time with matter)' and transient of $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$, but scope of $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ is limited to 'space-time with matter' and it is not well extended and discussed in details to 'charged space-time', and not extended and discussed in details to 'vibrating space-time'. Also, Definitions of PS_{UE} , IS_{UE} , VS_{UE} , CS_{UE} , I space, V space, C space are not mentioned in this research article. So, the space transformation model, space-matter transformation model, model for 'dimension of observable universe [2] and beyond' are in its very basic level which do not include explanation for unification of classical mechanics [22] and quantum mechanics [23], for singularity [4], and for unified gravity [9] in this research article. Similar the space definitions and methods here do not include any mathematical values.

Next crucial research to follow shall include definitions of PS_{UE} , IS_{UE} , VS_{UE} , CS_{UE} , I space, V space, C space with its physical properties like energy, mass, force and more. These definitions shall advance the definition of P space, the models for space transformation, model for space-matter transformation, and model for ‘finite-infinite dimension’. Especially, it shall advance model of ‘end to end dimension’, shall extend scope of $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ to ‘charged space- time’, to ‘vibrating space- time’ and that will put more light on understanding of observable universe [2]. Also, the most important open questions for gravity collapse at horizon of black hole [30], singularity [4], and unified gravity [9] to be answered with following up research.

To know the mystery of the space is very important to know the mystery of the universe and beyond. To know the nature of the space is very important to know the nature of the universe and beyond. Which would be not possible without the existence of extra dimensions [12]. The extra dimensions are must require to unite quantum mechanics [23] and classical mechanics [22], and to describe true nature of the universe [2] and beyond, and to describe geometry, mathematical model of universe [2] and beyond.

The $P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ which is constant in physical nature is also called $C_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$, and $Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ which is variable in physical nature is also called $V_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$ are the dimensions of observable universe [2] and beyond. It is the ‘end to end dimension’ everything that exist and that non-exist fall within these dimensions. I may also called it as the ‘finite-infinite dimension’.

The finite and infinite limit of universe [2], the existence of space and matter and its boundaries. The limit or boundaries are covered by ‘dimensions of observable universe and beyond’, and the existence in between with its true nature of behavior is perfectly governed by space itself and by its transformation laws. It is the fundamental nature of entire existence that consider to unite quantum mechanics [23] and classical mechanics [22] and beyond. It covers true dimension of observable universe [2] and beyond. It simplifies dimension of existence and non-existence (beyond the universe).

There are possibilities that with future progress of this research may require and may cause any changes in naming of space, in naming of dimension, in definition of standard model [11], in nature of space-time [1], in definition of universe [2] with its contents and universal law, definition of gravity [29], even it may cause any changes in understanding of dark matter [6] and dark energy [15].

13 Conclusions

This research article represents fundamental of entire existence of the space, matter and universe [2], like what is it? Where does it come from? How does it come? And how does it exist? And what is the gravity? It explains existence of space, matter, space-time [1] with matter and extra dimensions at very fundamental level. By defining 'end to end dimension', all the existence of space, matter, observable universe [2] and beyond falls within range of these dimensions. This extra dimensions will play important role to describe geometry, mathematical model of universe and beyond. With the definition of space, space transformation method, space-matter transformation method, space laws and extra dimensions, it demonstrate fundamental behavior of entire existence and establish fundamental relationship between space and matter which fall within these 'finite to infinite dimension'.

The definitions of GODEYE, GODEYE Model explain the phenomena of universe expansion-contraction and phenomena of gravity-anti gravity and gravitational force-anti gravitational force at very fundamental level for the dimension of observable universe and beyond.

While all other properties already included in P space definition only. The methods and models represented here are at its very basic level. It's mostly limited to physical properties of volume, as the definitions for P space element, I space and its element, V space and its element, and C space and its element are pending for follow up research. This theoretical research is the foundation for follow up future research in continuation with more definitions, advance methods, models with more properties like energy, time, mass, force and more. In the future, the subject of dimension of observable universe [2] and beyond shall be broaden by involving behavior of time dimension and other properties of space and matter.

This research being the foundation, will be applied to carry out more research in future. Those include advanced model for space transformation, advance model of dimension, dimension transformation, end to end gravity, singularity [4], gravity collapse at horizon of black hole [5], theory of everything [5], expansion-contraction of space & universe, dark matter [6] and dark energy [15].

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Appendix A

Abbreviations

C space : Charged space	11
$C_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$: Constant Dimension	10
CS_{UE} : Charged space unit element.....	13
I space : Invisible space	11
IS_{UE} : Invisible space unit element	12
P space : Pure space.....	11
$P_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$: Dimension of space-time only	9
PS_{UE} : Pure space unit element	12
$Q_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$: Dimension of space-time with matter	9
V space : Vibrating space	11
$V_{(X, Y, Z, T)}$: Variable Dimension	11
$VS_{UE L}$: Vibrating space unit element	12

Appendix B**Synonyms**

1. Dimension of Observable Universe and beyond	7
2. dimension of totality of existence.....	20
3. End to End dimension	8
4. finite to infinite dimension	24
5. finite-infinite dimension	23

Here, 1,2,3,4 and 5 are synonyms.

Appendix C

SYMBOLS

Pure space unit element graphically and visually represented as under

Multiple pure space unit elements graphically and visually represented as under

